

Development of ablative material for planetary entry

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ABSTRACT

A new-concept light weight ablator is developed. This ablator is phenolic resin-based and has layered structure and a mean density of approx. 0.6 gr/cm^3 which is less than one half of that of the previous ablators. Surface recession after 120sec heating (heat flux : approx. 4 MW/m^2 , impact pressure : approx. 1 atmosphere) is less than 2 mm. This result shows that the ablator has a potential to apply to capsules entering planets such as Venus and Mars. Various knowledge which has been obtained during developing the ablator is reported.

Keywords: ablative material, ablator, layered ablator

1. Introduction

A capsule for planetary entry encounters severe environment of high heat flux and high impact pressure. For example, in a direct entry to Venus atmosphere, a capsule with a ballistic coefficient of 500 kg/m^2 encounters the heating environment with approx. 10 MW/m^2 heat flux and approx. 1 atmosphere impact pressure. Usually high density ablators are required to endure the planetary entry environment [1][2], which causes payload weight reduction of the capsule.

ISAS (Institute of Space and Astronautical Science, Japan) is planning planetary missions to Venus and Mars, and planing Reentry Technology EXperiment (RTEX) for them using EXPRESS (EXPeriment Re-Entry Space System) earth-reentry capsule which is of a joint project between Japan and Germany. In 'RTEX' experiment, an ablator will be evaluated in actual reentry flight conditions (heat flux : approx. 4 MW/m^2 , impact pressure : approx. 1 atmosphere). In order to develop a light weight ablator for the mission, various ablative materials have been produced for trial and evaluated by arc-heater which simulates the heating environment.

2. Test facility and test method

To evaluate ablative material, an open-to-air type arc-heater was used which can provide high cold wall heat flux and high impact pressure at the same time to simulates heating environment [3].

Ablator test pieces are cylinder-shaped with 30 mm diameter and flat front surfaces. Thermocouples are installed in some of the ablator test pieces for temperature measurement. Side walls of test pieces are protected from extra heating by glass fiber cloths (in early stage of heating tests) or ablator tubes (for layered ablators).

Ablator test pieces are exposed into flow of arc-heater for the required time. The Gardon gauge measures heat flux before and after the exposure of the test pieces.

3. Basic research

Our company had already developed a silicon resin-based ablator which endures moderate earth reentry environment (heat flux : 2.4 MW/m², impact pressure : much less than 1atm). First of all, this ablator was tested by arc-heater which simulate 'EXPRESS' heating environment (heat flux : 4 MW/m² approx., impact pressure : 1atm approx.). But this silicon resin-based ablator could not endure this environment any longer since it's surface recession rate was over 5 mm/sec. Although further improvement of this ablator was conducted, test result showed that the silicon resin-based ablator is weak under high impact pressure, and that impact pressure greatly affects recession performance of ablators.

To find ablative materials with less recession, several kinds of ablators which consist of the combination of various materials were produced for trial and evaluated by arc heater. One categorized group is epoxy resin-based ablators (Table 1), and the other group is phenolic resin-based ablators (Table 2). Phenolic microballoons or silica microballoons were used for weight reduction, and chopped fibers or fiber cloths were used for reinforcement and less surface recession.

Table 1. Test case matrix of epoxy resin-based ablators

Ablator type	Fiber	Silica	Carbon	None
	Microballoons			
Chopped fiber and honeycomb reinforced(Apollo type)	Phenol	●	●	
	Silica	●	●	
	None			
Chopped fiber reinforced	Phenol	●		
	Silica			
	None	●		●
Fiber cloth layered	Phenol			
	Silica			
	None	●		

Table 2. Test case matrix of phenolic resin-based ablators

Ablator type	Fiber	Silica	Carbon	Silica - Alumina	Alumina	None
	Microballoons					
Chopped fiber reinforced	Phenol	●	●	●	●	
	None	●	●	●	●	●
Fiber cloth layered	Phenol	●	●			
	None	●	●			

It is very difficult to find a light weight ablator (goal: $0.5\text{gr}/\text{cm}^3$) with less recession rate (goal: less than $0.1\text{mm}/\text{sec}$ under the 'EXPRESS' heating environment). Test result showed that there is no ablator which satisfies our requirement (see Figure 1 for example). But various beneficial knowledge was obtained as follows:

- 1) In general phenolic resin-based ablators are superior to epoxy resin-based ablators from viewpoints as follows:
 - Surface recession performance (see Figure 2 for example)
 - Strength of charred layer
 - Thickness of charred layer (phenolic based > epoxy based)
- 2) Fiber reinforcement greatly improves surface recession performance (see Figure 2).
- 3) Honeycomb reinforcement (glass phenolic) is not effective to surface recession performance. Especially in the case of honeycomb & carbon fiber reinforcement type, the honeycomb is recessed faster than the base ablator, so the base ablator sometimes drops out.
- 4) In general silica fiber reinforcement is superior to other fiber reinforcement from viewpoint of surface recession performance and heat insulation performance.
- 5) Surface recession performances of two reinforcement types (chopped fiber, fiber cloth) are roughly the same level.

Figure 1. Surface recession performance of phenolic resin-based ablators

Figure 2. Influence of resin difference and fiber existence on recession rate

4. Development of a new concept ablator

To satisfy the two inconsistent requirements (low density, less recession rate), a new phenolic resin-based ablator with the layered structure was conceived (see Figure 2). Material selection is based on the previous basic research, i.e. the surface layer consists of phenolic resin and chopped silica fibers, and the inner layer consists of phenolic resin, chopped silica fibers and phenolic microballoons.

Figure 3. Concept of layered ablator

Figure 4 shows typical relationship between surface recession rate and heat flux imposed on the layered ablator, the surface recession performance is quite excellent (Figure 4). Figure 5 shows typical relationship between charred layer thickness and heat flux imposed on the layered ablator. Test results indicate that the ablator is a stable charring ablator (Figure 4, Figure 5). In long heating duration cases (120sec) the charred layer thickness is larger than the surface layer thickness, but there was no major damage which caused the surface layer to come off.

On the other hand, to assure material strength during launch and reentry, a shock impact test and a random vibration test were performed with post heating test pieces and virgin test pieces. No problem was recognized in those tests.

Figure 4. Relationship between surface recession rate and heat flux (phenolic resin-based layered ablator)

Figure 5. Relationship between charred layer thickness and heat flux (phenolic resin-based layered ablator)

5. Conclusion

It seems difficult to satisfy the two inconsistent requirements (low density, less recession rate under high heat flux and high impact pressure). The phenolic resin-based layered ablator is one of solutions for this problem. On such severe heating conditions as the above, this ablator can increase payload weight of reentry capsules.

6. Acknowledgment

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7. References

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